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ABSTRACTS

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Investigating Simple & Innovative Approaches for Point-of-Care Pancreatic α -Amylase Colorimetric Detection in Paper Devices

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Abstract: Acute pancreatitis (AP) is a common serious abdominal illness of the digestive system. Several biomarkers have been identified to be known for the diagnosis of AP secreted from pancreatic acinar cells like amylase, proenzyme trypsinogen, and lipase. A higher level of α -amylase enzyme in human serum is a suggestive indication of the onset of pancreatitis. In this, we aim to investigate simple & innovative approaches for pancreatic α -amylase detection conjoined with different bio-functionalization techniques on a paper-based microfluidic platform. Surface functionalization is carried out in paper devices to improve the sensitivity of detection assay as the surface treatments bring certain changes/modifications in the physicochemical properties, thus surging their performances. Paper coatings included: Chitosan, polyethylene glycol, PEG - Chitosan, AuNP-APTES, and Chitosan Nano powder, CNP. Three different detection approaches on functionalized paper devices are studied, (i) Starch-povidone conjugate, (ii) Starch-stabilized silver-copper nanoparticles (SI-Ag-CuNP), and, (iii) Starch- Iodine conjugated with pH indicator. In all the above reactions, a swift change in color was observed immediately after the addition of amylase. A good color gradient was observed in all four coatings whereas PEG-Chitosan, chitosan, and CNP showed better color gradients as compared to others. Non coated device failed to show any gradient. All the above approaches showed good colorimetric demarcation from control when used with acute pancreatitis sera samples. The new sensing methods for pancreatic α -amylase detection can be a potential point of care device for early screening for acute pancreatitis in low-resource settings or home users with abdominal pain.

Keywords: Paper-based devices, acute pancreatitis, α -amylase, surface bio functionalization, colorimetric detection.

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